

Search for New Amoebacides. Part V. Synthesis of Indan-pyrrolidines

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A few *N*-alkylated indan-pyrrolidines have been prepared by LiAlH_4 reduction of indane 1,2-dicarboxy-*N*-alkyl imides with the object of testing their amoebacidal activity.

Conessine (I), a steroidal alkaloid present in *Holarrhena antidysenterica* (Indian Kurchi) possesses anti-amoebic activity. If the rings A and B are abolished in conessine, it leads to a hexahydroindan-pyrrolidine of the type (II), which was named by Haworth and Michael (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4973) as dihydro-*des*-AB-con-8-eine. Little work appears to have been done on indan-pyrroles and indan-pyrrolidines. Syntheses of indan-pyrrolidines of type (III) have therefore been undertaken to ascertain their amoebacidal activity. Winans and Adkins (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 4167) reported formation of 2-methyl-3-ethoxycarbonyl-4,5-indenopyrrole by the interaction of isonitrosohydrindone and ethyl acetoacetate under high pressure hydrogenation in presence of Ni-catalyst. Bondietti and Lions (*J. Proc. Roy. Soc., N. S. Wales*, 1933, 66, 477) reported a synthesis of 2-methyl-3-acetyl-4,5-indeno-1,2-pyrrole.

Indan-pyrrolidines (III) have been synthesised on the following route :

Ethyl indene-1,2-dicarboxylate (Bougault, *Compt. rend.*, 1914, 159, 745) and its 5,6-dimethoxy derivative (Horning *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5826) were hydrogenated in presence

of Ni-catalyst. Indan-dicarboxy esters (A), thus formed, were heated with an appropriate alkylamine to yield imides (B). A portion of the reaction product always yielded diamide, which on further heating did not yield imide; it was considered to be a *trans*-diamide. The imides have been smoothly reduced by LiAlH_4 to the desired indan-pyrrolidines (III).

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl Indan-1,2-dicarboxyate (A : X = H).—Ethyl indene-1,2-dicarboxylate was hydrogenated in presence of Raney nickel, b.p. $160-62^\circ/2.4$ mm.

Ethyl indan-5,6-dimethoxy-1,2-dicarboxylate (A : X = 5,6-OMe) was prepared by hydrogenation of the corresponding indene. It was crystallised from petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$), m.p. $91-92^\circ$.

Indan-1,2-dicarboxy-N-alkylimide (B).—Indan-1,2-dicarboxy ester (0.02 M) was heated with a primary alkylamine (0.1M) in a sealed tube in a water bath or in an oil bath (150°) for 8 hours. On removal of excess amine the product was heated till the amine had ceased to evolve. The imide was recovered by either crystallisation from hot water or by extraction with petroleum ether ($60-80^\circ$) and subsequent distillation of the extract. Table I shows the characteristics of different imides.

TABLE I

R.	Method of recovery.	M.P./B.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.		M.P./B.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
			B : X = H.				B : X = 5,6-OMe.		
Me	a	71-72°	$\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	6.6	6.8	120-22°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	5.1	5.3
Et	a	78-80°	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	6.3	6.4	119-20°	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	5.2	5.0
Pr ^a	b	155-58°/1mm	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	5.7	6.0	84-86°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	5.0	4.8
Bu ^a	b	170-74°/0.6	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	5.8	5.7	215-17°/0.5mm	$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	4.6	4.6
Amyl ^b	b	195-97°/3.5	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	5.6	5.4	230-32°/3.5	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	4.3	4.4

(a) By crystallisation from hot water.

(b) Extracted with pet. ether ($60-80^\circ$); ether was removed and the residual liquid was distilled *in vacuo*.

Indan-1,2-dicarboxy-N-methylimide was also prepared in a different manner. Indan-1,2-dicarboxy ester on heating with liquor ammonia in a sealed tube afforded imides in poor yield. The latter was crystallised from hot water, m.p. $170-72^\circ$. (Found : N, 7.6. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 7.4%).

N-Potassio-derivative was prepared in quantitative yield by addition of ethanolic KOH to the imide solution in ethanol. Potassio-derivative of the imide on heating in benzene solution with excess of methyl iodide on a water bath for 8 hours yielded *N*-methyl compound in good yield (80%), proved identical with that prepared by the previous method.

Indan-N-alkylpyrrolidine (III).—Indan-1,2-dicarboxy-*N*-alkylimide was reduced with LiAlH_4 in dry ether. Pyrrolidine was then recovered by extraction of the ether solution with HCl (dil.). The latter was basified with NaOH solution and extracted with ether. The ether solution was dehydrated and distilled. Table II shows characteristics of different compounds.

TABLE II

R.	B.P.	Picrates.			Hydrochlorides.			
		M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen. Found. Calc.	M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
III : X = H.								
Me	104-106°/1.7 mm	188-90°	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₇ N ₄	13.6 13.9	125°	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ NCl	C : 68.5 H : 8.0	68.7 7.6
Et	104-106°/0.7	179-80°	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₇ N ₄	13.2 13.4	145°	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ NCl	C : 69.7 H : 8.2	69.8 8.0
Pr ⁿ	115-17°/0.6	170-72°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₇ N ₄	13.0 13.0	120°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ NCl	C : 70.4 H : 8.7	70.7 8.4
Bu ⁿ	122-25°/0.6	174-76°	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₇ N ₄	12.4 12.6	158°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ NCl	C : 71.8 H : 9.0	71.6 8.7
Amy ⁿ	150-52°/3.5	147-49°	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₇ N ₄	11.9 12.2	..			
III : X = 6,7-OMe.								
Me	155-58°/1.5 mm	192-94°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₉ N ₄	11.9 12.1	164°	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₇ NCl	C : 62.1 H : 7.6	62.3 7.4
Et	155-57°/0.8	175-76°	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₉ N ₄	11.6 11.7	213°	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₈ NCl	C : 63.1 H : 7.9	63.5 7.7
Pr ⁿ	160-62°/1.5	182-84°	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₉ N ₄	11.2 11.4	161°	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₈ NCl	C : 64.2 H : 8.2	64.5 8.0
Bu ⁿ	168-70°/0.6	162-64°	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₉ N ₄	10.8 11.1	162°	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₈ NCl	C : 65.2 H : 8.5	65.5 8.4
Amy ^l	160-62°/0.6	166-68°	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ O ₉ N ₄	10.7 10.8	..			

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